

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B500		
Date:	21/1/10		
Take Off:	10:37:21Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:33:27Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 22m51s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Sea / North West Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
5	Flight Mananger	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS training	Angela Dean	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	CVI	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
9	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
10	Mini-LIDAR	Franco Marengo	Met Office
11	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
12	SID3	Edwin Hirst	Uni Herts
13	Dropmaster	Doug Anderson	FAAM
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
Y	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flighter log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-21	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

B500

21/01/2010

CONSTRAIN Flight 5

Sortie S4: Snow evolution in deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus.

Deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus layers associated with cold fronts are required for observations of snow evolution when aggregation and sedimentation dominates the cloud evolution rather than ice nucleation or dynamics.

Ice crystal shape or capacitance factor controls how efficiently the ice crystal acts as a source or sink of water vapour by depositional growth.

Weather

Altostratus and cirrostratus associated with cold front, absence of embedded convection.

Sortie location

Northwest coast.

Sortie summary

Perform a Lagrangian descent during which the aircraft drifts with the horizontal wind and descending at a rate similar to the mass weighted fallspeed of snow particles. Lagrangian descent over few km.

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area at best-range speed and altitude (FL200).
- 2) **Profile ascent** through cloud until 1000ft above cloud top or maximum altitude. During profile, determine average wind direction. All runs are orientated perpendicular to this mean wind direction.
- 3) **Dropsonde run**: Perform straight and level 1000ft above cloud top. Lidar reports cloud top height. Dropsonde.
- 4) Descend into cloud layer.
- 5) **Cloud penetration runs**: Perform a descending Lagrangian descent, drifting with the horizontal wind to repeatedly sample cloud. The flight path is a race-track (one side is a straight and level run (5 min) and the other side is a profile descent (400ft/min). Initial turn direction is specified by mission scientist.
- 6) **Repeat** items 2 to 5 as time permits.
- 7) **Return transit** at best range speed.

Instrument requirements

Dropsonde launch locations critical, must be in region of Lagrangian descent.

CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode. No varying cut-size or changing to aerosol mode.

Nevozorov zeroed once only when at high level early in flight.

Lidar operated to identify cloud base. No varying integration time or changing the display.

b500 10:13:20-16:12:34

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 21-01-10

Flight No: B 500

Pre-Flighter: STEVE COWAN

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<i>N₂ 90 O₂ = 170</i>
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	<i>N₂ = 55 bar CO₂/Ar = 145 bar</i>
3		Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5		Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6		Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Helmann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	<i>In cockpit</i>
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	x	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	x	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	x	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	x	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	x	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	x	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	x	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	x	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	x	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	x	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	x	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36		Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	x	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Helmann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48		All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51		Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>Signed</u>
53		ICEX applied		
54		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

Mission Scientist's Log

CONSTRAIN
Flight 5

Flight No **B.500** Date 21/01/10 Name Paul Brown Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1039					1/0
1047		9300		just N of Arran.	7/8 low cloud below, deeper patches of upper cloud just above this level.
1050		15500			now in ice cloud.
/		22000			wind 16ms ⁻¹ / 245 deg.
105848		24000			End Profile start R1.
110416	P1				Start Profile for 260 initially.
		25000			wind 15 / 250.
110732	P1	26000			End
111057	P2	"			Profile for 280
		28000			14 / 265
111835		"			Sonde 1.
112101		"			End Run. turn R, takes us E into slightly clearer air.
112353		"			Start P3.1 for 26000 400ft/min. should be close to cloud top
/		27000			14 / 190
11290	P3.1				End.
113138	.	26000	335		Run 3.2 14/265 Cloud cloud top 23000 low but variable. poss base 2000. Thicker cloud is still to the W.
113638	R3.2	"			End, turn R.
/					Cloud top below has sub-son.
113858	P3.3	26000			Start winds rubbish
	'	24000			End due to frozen

A07A

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B500** Date 21/1/10 Name Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115100	R3.3	24000			End. some patches of cloud pattern.
115308	P3.3	"			Start. 400ft/min.
		22000			P3.3 End.
120020	R3.4	22000			Start. -29°C
120230					Thru thicker patch, and ice falling from above.
120523	R3.4	"			End.
120724	P3.4				Start. 400ft/min.
121026					descending thro patchy supercooled LWC ~0.05
	P3.4	20000			End.
121427	R3.5	"			Start. light icing on port side.
121929	"				End. In cloud at end of run.
					Structure remains patchy & with complex vertical structure.
122138	P3.5	20000			Start.
122530					supercooled water again. wind still 240.
					Fall streaks visible below the water cloud layer to SW of run end
122828	R3.6	18000			
123523	P3.6				Start. still patchy ahead.
124024	End	16000			quite clear below at SW of run.
124220	R3.7	16000			varying patches of ice.

precip below this level. Lidar reports it going down to 10000ft, optically thin.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B500** Date 2/1/10 Name Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124222	3.7	16000			End & Start P4 for 33000
					returning to Stonaway.
///		23000			conv. in clear between layers.
///					patches of low cloud ahead & left, pass assoc with waves in lee of Hebrides.
125152		26500			230 wind dir.
		30000	202		cloud., 230 wind.
		32500			contrailing.
130912	R4.1	33000	315		End P4, Start 4.1
131150					sonde 2 some thin cloud above, but seem to be in generally more uniform region. sonde good.
131418		//			End 4.1 300pm rosettes,
1316	P4.1				Start. Back +4 on ambient. -58C
///					cloud top seems occasionally visible above.
					23-30C 2DC • 03 cm ³ CIP
132042					hollow columns & rosettes - all prob. ice.
132219	P4.1	31000			End.
					lidar, thick but base at 23-27000 ?
132434	R4-2	31000			Start.
132937	R4.2				End. Cloud under more uniform along run.
133151	P4.2	//	130	58.42.0 07 0.0	SIDs both OK. mostly small.
133607	//	29000			End. Some signs of aggregation.
133921	R4.3	//	332		Start. bit of heading deviation on the track but should end at about the right point.
///					

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B500** Date 21/1/10 Name Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134409	R4.3	29000			End, larger excursions in Nev
—					TCW during boom.
134632	P4.3		137		
135130		27000			End. chain aggregates apparently. rosettes & hollow columns.
135340	R4.4	27000	310		Thicker spike of cloud near start.
135840		- /			End.
140053	P4.4				Start. 400ft/min. with son on the R.
—					New TCW varying.
140546	//	25000	131		End. more of a gap layer open to the left. lidar increased backscatter
—					Turning into thicker cloud
140754	R4.5	25000	310		still in thicker patch, similar to start of last level leg.
—					CP1 - reporting supercooled LWC ?
—					no riming
141255	//	//			End. Pass in gap.
141458	P4.5	25000	132		seem to be more clear of cloud on S. bound, descending leg.
141950		23000			End.
142204	R4.6	//	310		Start. only small Nevz. patch at start.
142707		//			End. Pass been through region of bullet evaporation.
142901	P4.6	//	135		Start. impression S bound N bound
1432					lidar, big increase in backscatter.
143602	R4.7	21000	310		Start.
144111					End

1.5 hrs
on back

144333 P4.7

Start $\frac{200m}{15min}$

atwo
©

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B500** Date 21/1/10 Name Page 55 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144622					Similar structure in cloud, between layers initially
—					but coming into denser region
—					Sideplanes on CPI
144814	P6.7	19000			End. Newz. Taw baseline about on zero.
145011	R4.8	"			
145511		19000			End in dense patch,
—					New $\sim 0.02 \text{ gm}^{-3}$
—					Some signs of repeating structure between Nbound
—					legs
145705	P4.8	19000	132		still seem to be in slight larger gap near start of run
150213		17000			End
150400	R4.9	17000	310		Start. — final leg.
—					highest peaks in 1wc just before start of run.
150900	R4.9	"			End and start P5 in climbing turn.
—	P5	31000			Above a lot of cloud but still thin Ci above.
152811	P5	35000			Overhead stormway.
—					start run; before descent.
1549		18500			Some good piles of plates, Acker over mtus on W-Coast

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B500

Date:21/1/2010

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:NW Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
102531		Start-Up	0.00 kft	073	
102957		taxy	0.00 kft	073	
103721		T/O	-.03 kft	121	Prestwick
105848	110416	Run 1	24.0 kft	342	
110416	110732	Profile 1	24.4 - 26.0 kft	341	
110732	111057	Run 2	26.0 kft	342	
111057	111320	Profile 2	26.0 - 28.0 kft	342	
111320	112102	Run 3.1	28.0 kft	343	
111832		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	335	
112353	112901	Profile 3.1	28.0 - 26.0 kft	153	
112829		jw/nevz zero	26.3 kft	153	
113138	113641	Run 3.2	26.0 - 26.1 kft	327	
113640		MPDS LOst	26.1 kft	335	
113858	114347	Profile 3.2	26.1 - 24.0 kft	152	
114602	115100	Run 3.3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	328	
115314	115816	Profile 3.3	24.1 - 22.0 kft	150	
120020	120523	Run 3.4	22.1 - 22.0 kft	327	
120724	121225	Profile 3.4	22.1 - 20.0 kft	149	
121427	121929	Run 3.5	20.1 - 20.0 kft	327	
122138	122634	Profile 3.5	20.1 - 18.1 kft	151	
122828	123331	Run 3.6	18.1 kft	327	
123523	124024	Profile 3.6	18.1 - 16.0 kft	149	
124220	124722	Run 3.7	16.1 - 16.0 kft	327	
124731	130911	Profile 4	16.1 - 33.0 kft	332	
130912	131418	Run 4.1	33.0 kft	313	
131153		sonde 2	33.0 kft	312	
131724	132219	Profile 4.1	33.0 - 31.0 kft	134	
132434	132937	Run 4.2	31.1 kft	306	
133151	133651	Profile 4.2	31.1 - 29.0 kft	130	
133921	134409	Run 4.3	29.1 - 29.0 kft	328	
134632	135130	Profile 4.3	29.1 - 27.1 kft	135	
135340	135841	Run 4.4	27.1 - 27.0 kft	308	
140052	140546	Profile 4.4	27.1 - 25.0 kft	131	

140754	141255	Run 4.5	25.1 - 25.0 kft	307
141458	142000	Profile 4.5	25.1 - 23.0 kft	130
142204	142705	Run 4.6	23.1 - 23.0 kft	307
142901	143402	Profile 4.6	23.1 - 21.0 kft	130
143602	144111	Run 4.7	21.1 - 21.0 kft	306
144323	144814	Profile 4.7	21.1 - 19.1 kft	133
145011	145511	Run 4.8	19.0 kft	306
145705	150213	Profile 4.8	19.0 - 17.0 kft	128
150400	150900	Run 4.9	17.0 kft	308
150901	152810	Profile 5	17.0 - 35.0 kft	314
152811	153929	Run 5	35.0 kft	172
161048		Land	0.09 kft	121 Prestwick

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B500

Date: 21 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. Turbulence Probe iced. Suspect ports not emptied pre-flight.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Cloud Physics Flight Log B500

Date:21/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:08:00:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.04	Vref (>7V):	5.4	El#1 V (>1):	1.1	El#1 V (>1):	3.2	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-1.1
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.2	El#32 V (>1):	3.1	El#32 V (>1):	3.6	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-1.1
			Sheath flow	14.35	El#64 V (>1)	1.29	El#64 V (>1)	3.15				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
08:44:46			15	Noise								
08:46:18			20									
08:47:46			30									
08:49:38			40									
10:58:47	FL240											Start Run 1
10:59:00						0.0001		1	600	10	1	
11:01:00						0.0001		40	500	10	1	
11:03:00		0.02	30			0.015		20	425	8	1	
11:04:14	FL240											End of Run & start Profile 1
11:05:53	FL250	0.04	45			0.005		10	800	9	1.5	
11:07:32	FL260											End of Profile & start Run 2
11:08:00		0.04	45			0.005		16	700	8	1	
11:10:00		0.04	45			0.005		35	350	8	1	
11:10:54	FL260											End of Run & Start Profile 3
11:11:57	FL270					0.005		10	500	8	0.5	
11:13:20	FL280											End of Profile & Start Run 3.1

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
11:14:00	FL280					0.001		2	300	10	0.1	
11:16:00						0.001		16	200	10	0.5	
11:18:00						0.001		16	200	10	0.2	
11:20:00						0.0001		20	200	10	0.2	
11:21:04												End of Run
11:23:53	FL280											Start Profile 3.1
11:26:10	FL270											
11:29:00	FL260											End of Profile
11:31:39	FL260											Start Run 3.2
11:32:00						0.0001		2	225	10	0.3	
11:34:00						0.0001		0.5			0.01	
11:36:00												
11:36:38												End of Run
11:38:50	FL260											Start Profile 3.2
11:41:04	FL250											
11:43:46	FL240										0.01	End of Profile
11:45:59	FL240											Start Run 3.3
11:46:00												
11:48:00						0.0001		0.5			0.1	
11:50:00		0.04	45			0.014		50	100	10	0.1	
11:51:00												End of Run
11:53:15	FL240											Start Profile 3.3
11:55:37	FL230											
11:58:16	FL220											End of Profile
12:00:19	FL220											Start Run 3.4
12:01:00		8	20			0.0001		0.5	200	10	60	
12:03:00		1	15			0.0001					20	
12:05:21												End of Run
12:07:25	FL220											Start Profile 3.4
12:09:55	FL210	3	17								40	
12:12:24	FL200	8	22					0.5	700	8	80	End of Profile
12:14:26	FL200											Start Run 3.5
12:15:00												
12:17:00								0.5				
12:19:29												End of Run
12:21:35	FL200							0.5				Start Profile 3.5

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
12:23:56	FL190							0.5				
12:26:33	FL180							0.5				End of Profile
12:28:28	FL180											Start Run 3.6
12:29:00								1				
12:31:00								1				
12:33:37												End of Run
12:35:22	FL180	1	20			0.0005		2	600	8	1	Start Profile 3.6
12:37:41	FL170	5	20			0.0005		1	700	8	1	
12:40:22	FL160											End of profile
12:42:19	FL160											Start Run 3.7
12:43:00						0.0002		0.5	800	8		
12:45:00						0.0002		2	800	8	2	
12:47:20	FL160											End of Run & Start Profile 4
12:48:30	FL170					0.0001		5	800	8	2	
12:49:49	FL180					0.0001		3	700	8	2	
12:50:50	FL190					0.002		3	800	8	1	
12:51:42	FL200					0.004		10	600	8	1	
12:52:40	FL210					0.008		11	600	8	1	
12:53:33	FL220					0.003		3	750	4	1	
12:54:33	FL230					0.001		1			0.1	
12:55:30	FL240											
12:56:21	FL250											
12:57:18	FL260											
12:58:21	FL270											
12:59:35	FL280										0.1	
13:00:45	FL290	0.03	45									
13:02:17	FL300	0.04	40			0.0001		25	150	10	4	
13:04:12	FL310	0.04	45			0.001		25	150	10	0.2	
13:06:49	FL320					0.002		3	200	10	0.2	
13:09:12	FL330											End of Profile & Start Run 4
13:10:00		0.01	45			0.002		25	200	10	1	
13:12:00		0.01	45			0.0001		50	200	10	1	
13:14:00		0.01	45			0.004		25	275	10	1	
13:14:19												End of Run
13:17:18	FL330					0.001		40	250	10	1	Start Profile 4.1
13:19:37	FL320					0.003		22	500	10	1	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
13:22:19	FL310					0.001		10	300	10	1	End of Profile
13:24:35	FL310	1.1	25			0.004		15	300	10	25	Start Run 4.2
13:28:00						0.004		22	400	10	1	
13:29:40												End of Run 4.2
13:31:52	FL310					0.004		25	300	10	1	Start Profile 4.2
13:34:21	FL300					0.003		15	200	10	1	
13:36:52	FL290	0.03	25			0.0001		50	200	10	2	End of Profile
13:39:19	FL290											Start Run 4.3
13:40:00		0.03	45			0.008		35	250	10	1	
13:42:00						.0.004		10	700	4	2	
13:44:10												End of Run
13:46:28	FL290					0.005		20	300	4	1	Start Profile 4.3
13:48:48	FL280					0.004		20	300	4	1	
13:51:29	FL270	0.04	50			0.001		60	200	10	80	
13:53:40	FL270											Start Run 4.4
13:54:00						0.005		125	200	10	4	
13:56:00		0.01	45			0.012		180	500	10	5	
13:59:51												End of Run
14:00:54	FL270					0.005		25	325	10	0.5	Start Profile 4.4
14:03:01	FL260							2	100	10	0.3	
14:05:45	FL250					0.005		140	250	10	4	End of Profile
14:07:56	FL250											Start Run 4.5
14:08:00						0.005		90	275	10	4	
14:10:00						0.005		20	250	10	4	
14:12:00						0.005		8	700	4	2	
14:12:54												End of Run
14:14:57	FL250					0.0001		10	150	10	0.1	Start Profile 4.5
14:17:25	FL240	0.02	40			0.0001		3	250	10	0.3	
14:19:58	FL230					0.005		1	275	10	0.5	End of Profile
14:22:06	FL230											Start Run 4.6
14:23:00		0.05	20			0.002		25	200	10	0.5	
14:25:00						0.008		24	200	10	1	
14:27:02												End of Run
14:29:03	FL230	0.01	30			0.0001		15	200	10	0.2	Start Profile 4.6
14:31:27	FL220	0.02	30			0.0001						
14:33:02	FL210					0.0001		25	200	10	1	End of Profile

Cloud Physics Flight Log B500

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
14:36:01	FL210											Start Run 4.7
14:37:00						0.01		40	250	10	1	
14:39:00						0.008		54	600	10	2.5	
14:41:08												End of Run
14:43:13	FL210					0.01		5	300	10	0.5	Start Profile 4.7
14:45:29	FL200					0.005		5	350	10	1	
14:48:14	FL190					0.005		25	400	10	0.5	End of Profile
14:50:10	FL190											Start Run 4.8
14:51:00						0.0125		25	400	10	0.5	
14:53:00						0.0175		40	550	4	2.5	
14:55:10												End of Run
14:57:05	FL190					0.0025		4	700	8	0.2	Start Profile 4.8
14:59:26	FL180					0.0025		6	700	8	1	
15:02:08	FL170					0.0025		20	600	8	1.5	End of Profile
15:04:00	FL170					0.01		43	675	8	5	Start Run 4.9
15:06:00						0.008		7	575	8	1	
15:08:00						0.01		25	600	8	3	
15:09:00	FL170					0.012		45	650	8	7	End of Run & Start Profile 5
15:10:09	FL180					0.002		3	650	8	1	
15:11:00	FL190					0.004		15	525	8	2	
15:12:01	FL200					0.018		35	600	8	2	
15:12:55	FL210					0.015		12	600	9	1	
15:14:00	FL220					0.0025		8	800	9	1	
15:14:39	FL230					0.0025		9	800	4	1	
15:15:31	FL240					0.0025		8	800	4	1	
15:16:27	FL250					0.0075		15	550	4	1	
15:17:16	FL260					0.0075		15	550	4	1	
15:18:16	FL270					0.01		20	350	4	1	
15:19:11	FL280					0.01		25	700	4	1	
15:20:14	FL290					0.005		15	500	10	1	
15:21:00	FL300					0.005		18	300	10	1	
15:21:59	FL310					0.0025		30	150	10	0.5	
15:23:16	FL320					0.0001		65	150	10	0.1	
15:24:37	FL330	0.08	35					35	125	11	1	
15:25:53	FL340	0.1	45					15	50	11	5	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
15:28:10	FL350	0.25	40					14	75	11	4	End of Profile & Start Run 5
15:30:00		0.1	30					7	50	11	1	
15:39:32												End of Run
15:41:00												LWC CIP15 test
15:44:00												LWC CIP 100

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:		N/A
	Flow:		
2DC	El#1:	-1.1	Switched off once in Flight briefly to reset probe
	El#32:	-1.5	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	5.1	Reference voltage too low
	Flow:		
CDP	Laser V:	3.51	
FFSSP	Ref V:		N/A
SID 3	Laser V:		
Rack Equipment			

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B500	Date	21/10/2010	Operator	Angela Dean	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
11:18:36	1	Launch	328.90 -44.90 75.87 267.60 15.20 -31.50 -6.475600 58.619300 8542.90
11:28:59	1	Land	1007.55 5.88 68.13 143.15 12.31 -9.78 -6.417980 58.687329 135.74
			Surface alt unknown not ticked
131154	2	Launch	261.50 -58.20 111.88 243.90 20.60 -34.70 -7.234300 58.370300 10070.60
132342	2	Land	1003.29 6.00 72.75 144.83 17.07 -9.60 -7.177808 58.479238 146.76
			End drop time override. Changed from 709.2 to 708.2 Surface alt unknown NOT ticked.

B500 21/1/10

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		<i>Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv</i>	<i>Nominally 34000 Hz</i>	<i>Nominally 7.5 Torr</i>	<i>Nominally 35 - 40 °C</i>
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
01/20/2010 16:25:57	Previous Flight	63.320	33115.80	N/A	N/A
01/21/2010 10:09:51	Pre-Flight/Gnd	68.478	35041.30	7.52	35.34
01/21/2010 11:01:44	24.0kft	67.286	33770.04	6.62	35.53
01/21/2010 11:34:53	26kft	67.120	33344.87	6.37	35.50
01/21/2010 12:17:25	20kft	65.548	33452.93	7.10	36.58
01/21/2010 13:28:21	31.1kft	65.124	32423.20	6.27S? F	40.37
01/21/2010 14:02:33	27.1kft	65.167	32498.80	6.36S	40.36
01/21/2010 14:53:05	21.1kft	64.440	33124.07	7.46	39.70
01/21/2010 15:32:08	35kft (start of transit home)	65.381	32606.13	5.44S	40.50
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv)	:	35041.30 Hz (As per pre flight cal)
NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	:	_____
Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	:	_____
CO Calibrations on automatic repeat?	:	NO Interval set? NO
NOx: 0.42, 0.47, 0.49, 0.47, 0.42, 0.39, 0.36, 0.37, 0.39, 0.44		
O3: -0.2, -0.2, -2.2, -0.4, -0.9, 0.3, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.3		

Mission Scientist De-Brief**1) Assessment of the flight**

The purpose of the sortie was to examine ice particle evolution in deep cirrus and altostratus cloud. The standard flight pattern element was a sequence of i) 5 minute straight/level leg, ii) turn to the right (~2 min), iii) 5 min leg descending at 400ft/min, iv) 180 deg turn to the right. Overall descent rate approx 0.7m/s. Two sets of patterns were flown.

The first set commenced at 28000ft, on the east side of the main frontal cloud band. The cloud conditions were multi-layered and patchy, the lidar picking out significant structure below the aircraft. Layers of supercooled liquid were encountered at several altitudes, at temperatures down to about -28C. When descending below a supercooled layer at around 20000ft, ice fallstreaks were clearly visible below the water cloud layer, but with a vertical extent of maybe only 2-300ft. The pattern was terminated after the level leg at 16000ft.

There was then a profile ascent to 33000ft. This entered a region that appeared to be more uniform ice cloud above an altitude of about 25000ft. The top of the profile was below the highest cirrus cloud tops.

The first level leg of a new sequence was flown at 33000ft in what appeared to be more continuous cloud, although still with horizontal structure in the ice water content. Near the top of the pattern, crystal habits in the CPI imagery were dominated by pristine crystals (bullet-rosettes and hollow columns) indicating predominantly depositional growth. During the descent, increasing signs of aggregation appeared. It was possible to trace structural features in the cloud layer between about 3 successive level legs or profiles. The descending legs were flown on the east side of the pattern and often appeared to be in less dense cloud. Denser cloud could be identified to the west and was penetrated during the level runs of the pattern. The final level leg was flown at 17000ft prior to a profile ascent to 35000ft and return transit. There was still thin cirrus cloud present above the 35000ft level.

2) Weather conditions

Fig. 1. MSLP analysis at 12Z. Dissipating occluded front over the operational area.

UK4 op Cloud amount
Thursday 1200Z 21/01/2010 (+3h)

no cloud low medium low+med high high+low high+med all
Fig 2. UK4 forecast cloud 12Z.

EIEA51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 21 Jan 2010 1745 UTC

Fig. 3. IR image at 1745Z – somewhat after the time of the flight but you get the idea....

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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AC power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect an AC adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

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80

160

240

320

Range: 320
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Gain: Min
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Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

AC power adapter detected in the docking station. The dock will be disabled and your system will operate on battery power. Please connect an AC adapter or higher to the dock for best system operation.

OK

80 160 240 320

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

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Gain: Min
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OK

80 160 240 320

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
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Range: 5

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Gain: Max

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